

A study on the Mirinae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Miridae) fauna of Amasya Province, Türkiye

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ABSTRACT: In this study, the research material consists of samples collected from 54 different localities in around Amasya province between 2020 and 2022. As a result of the determination of the material collected in Amasya province, 29 species belonging to the Mirinae subfamily were revealed. Of them, the rarely species *Polymerus holosericeus* is new record for Anatolia. The species *Adelphocoris detritus*, *Adelphocoris quadripunctatus*, *Capsus ater*, *Closterotomus krueperi*, *Orthops forelli* are also new record for the Miridae faunae of Black Sea Region and the species *Closterotomus fulvomaculatus*, *Phytocoris varipes*, *Polymerus brevicornis*, *Stenodema sericans* and *Notostira erratica* are also a new record for the Miridae faunae of Central Black Sea Region.

KEY WORDS: Heteroptera, Mirinae, the new record, Amasya, Black Sea Region, habitats.

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INTRODUCTION

The suborder Heteroptera (Hemiptera) has a large number of species, the majority of which are found in tropical regions. In the world, 45,000 species are known in

24 superfamilies belonging to seven suborders (Henry, 2017).

Of those 9365 species belonging to 1632 genera are known in the Palaearctic Region (Aukema et al., 2013; Fent &

Dursun, 2022). In Türkiye have been numerous studies of Heteroptera and as a result 1645 species have been listed (Çerçi & Koçak, 2023). Miridae, the largest family of Heteroptera has been listed about 11,500 species belonging to 1400 genera from the Palaearctic Region and distributed in almost all habitats (Kerzhner & Josifov, 1999; Henry, 2017). Therewithal, it is also of great importance as the family with the largest number of representatives (515 species) in Türkiye (Çerçi & Koçak, 2017; Çerçi et al. 2018; 2019; 2020; 2022; Tezcan, 2020).

The family Miridae consists of eight subfamilies; the most diverse are Mirinae, Orthotylinae and Phylinae. Mirinae is one of the largest subfamilies of Miridae with about 4000 species and accounts for 75% of the family Miridae in Palaearctic (Cassis et al., 2007).

The subfamily Mirinae is represented by 154 species belonging to 43 genera in Türkiye (Kerzhner & Josifov, 1999; Çerçi & Koçak, 2017; Çerçi et al., 2018; 2019; 2020; 2021; 2022).

Although many faunistic and systematic studies have been carried out so far, there is still a need for further study of the Miridae family in our country and in other countries. Ribes & Goula (1986) reviewed Wagner's entomological notes and published a catalog of 1410 Miridae species. Kerzhner and Josifov made a revision of the Palearctic Region Miridae catalog in 1999.

Türkiye has a rich Miridae fauna. Some of the studies conducted to evaluate the distribution and biogeography of Miridae in Türkiye are as follows: Hoberlandt 1955; Önder, 1976; Bingöl, 1978; Lodos et al., 1978; Altınayar, 1981; Önder et al., 1981; Yayla, 1983; Önder & Lodos, 1986; Özbek & Alaoğlu, 1987; Çam, 1988; Lodos et al., 1989; Önder et al., 1990; 1998; Güçlü et al., 1995; Çevik, 1996; Yaşarakıncı & Hıncal, 1997; 2000; Tezcan & Önder, 1999; 2003; Yıldırım et al., 1999; Öz Saraç & Kıyak, 2001; Lodos et al., 2003; Kıyak et al., 2004; Önder et

al., 2006; Yazıcı, 2015; Çerçi & Koçak, 2016, 2017; Çerçi & Dursun, 2017; Matocq, 2019a,b; Çerçi et al., 2018; 2019; 2020; 2022; Yazıcı et al. 2019; Kaçar & Dursun, 2022. In parallel with this diversity, many new species of Miridae were described here, and 84 of them have remained endemic to Türkiye to date (Dursun & Fent, 2017). In the last 5 years alone, 13 new Miridae species have been described from the country (Çerçi & Dursun, 2017; Günther & Strauss, 2018; Carapezza & Kment 2018; Sanchez & Cassis, 2018; Matocq, 2019a,b; Pagola-Carte, 2019; Çerçi et al., 2019; 2020; 2021). Çerçi et al., (2022), published Heteroptera species collected from many localities of Anatolia, especially Eastern Anatolia, between 1998 and 2021.

The Amasya province, with such a rich flora, harbors a rich fauna (Dursun, 2011). Until this study, there had been no specific study of the Mirinae subfamily in Amasya province. This study aimed to investigate the Mirinae fauna of the area in detail, and the findings obtained contribute to future studies.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study material was obtained from 54 localities with different vegetation and habitat in Amasya province in the years 2020 to 2022 (Fig. 1). The specimens were collected from the trees and under herbaceous vegetation and above ground with a sweep net (Table 1). All samples were put in tubes in 70% ethanol and brought to the laboratory. In the laboratory, specimens were softened in hot water (80°C-100°C) for preparation of the male genitalia which was used for further identifications. The specimens were prepared and identified using the relevant diagnostic and were investigated under a stereo microscope (Leica EZ4) and keys of Stichel (1960) and Wagner (1970/71). The material is deposited in the collection of Amasya University, Faculty of Science and Arts, Department

RESULTS**Hemiptera Linnaeus, 1758****Heteroptera Latreille, 1810****Miridae Hahn, 1833****Mirinae Hahn, 1833****Genus: *Adelphocoris* Reuter, 1896*****Adelphocoris detritus* (Fieber, 1861)****Material examined: Amasya:** Amasya Castle, 10.05.2022, 1♀.**Number of localities:** 1**Distribution in Türkiye:** Diyarbakır, Kütahya (Önder et al., 2006; Maral & Gökçe 2021).**Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe:** Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Great Britain, Italy, Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Asian Türkiye (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013; Heckmann et al., 2015).***Adelphocoris lineolatus* (Goeze, 1778)****Material examined: Amasya:** Uygur, 19.05.2021, 6♂♂; Tatar, 19.05.2021, 1♂, 1♀; Ezinepazar, 19.05.2021, 2♀♀; 22.06.2022, 4♀♀, 33♂♂; Sevincer, 05.07.2021, 1♀; İlyasköy, 05.07.2021, 2♂♂; Sanayi Sitesi, 24.08.2021, 29♀♀, 17♂♂; Gözlek, 03.09.2021, 40♀♀, 18♂♂; Kapıkaya, 09.09.2021, 2♂♂, 13♀♀; Bağlıca, 26.07.2022, 2♀♀. **Suluova:** Ayrancı, 28.06.2021, 1♂; Yüzbeyi, 28.06.2021, 7♀♀, 1♂; 18.08.2022, 1♂, 1♀; Deveci, 20.08.2021, 1♀; Saygılı, 14.07.2022, 3♀♀. **Merzifon:** Aktarla, 20.08.2021, 4♀♀, 1♂; Çobanören Yolu, 14.09.2021, 1♀. **Göynücek:** Merkez, 03.09.2021, 1♂; Şarklı, 03.09.2021, 1♀; Kafarlı, 23.08.2022, 2♀♀. **Taşova:** Yeşilyurt, 27.05.2021, 2♂♂; Kızılgüldüren Village, 10.07.2021, 5♀♀, 3♂♂; Destek Stream, 28.06.2022, 1♂. **Hamamözü:** 07.09.2021, 4♀♀, 1♂.**Number of localities:** 24**Distribution in Türkiye:** Adana, Ankara, Antalya, Bartın, Bolu, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Edirne, Elâzığ, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hatay, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırşehir, Kilis, Kırıkkale, Konya, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Sinop, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Lodos et al., 2003; Fent, 2011; Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı, 2015; Kivan & Dirik, 2016; Çerçi et al., 2018; Tolga & Yoldaş, 2019; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021).**Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe:** Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European Kazakhstan, European Türkiye, Finland, France, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldavia, Montenegro, The Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Azerbaijan, Afghanistan, Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, China, Georgia, Iran, Japan, Kirgizia, Korea, Mongolia, Russia, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan. **North Africa:** Algeria, Tunisia. **Extralimital:** Pakistan, Kashmir, North America

(introduced) (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013; Heckmann et al., 2015).

***Adelphocoris quadripunctatus* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Material examined: Amasya: Sarıyar, 19.05.2021, 3♂♂, 2♀♀; Uygur, 19.05.2021, 3♂♂, 1♀; Ezinepazar, 19.05.2021, 18♂♂, 5♀♀. **Taşova:** Yeşilyurt, 27.05.2021, 2♂♂, 3♀♀.

Number of localites: 4

Distribution in Türkiye: Aydın, Edirne, Erzurum, İzmir, Tekirdağ (Kivan & Dirik, 2016; Altın & Özder, 2020; Çerçi & Tezcan, 2021).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European Türkiye, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Moldavia, The Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Asian Kazakhstan, Asaian Türkiye, China, Israel?, Japan, Korea, Russia, Mongolia. **North Africa:** Egypt? (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013).

***Adelphocoris vandalicus* (Rossi, 1790)**

Material examined: Amasya: Boğazköy, 18.05.2021, 1♀. **Suluova:** Yüzbeyi, 28.06.2021, 1♂.

Number of localites: 2

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Artvin, Balıkesir, Bilecik, Bolu, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Edirne, Erzurum, Elâzığ, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Konya, Mersin, Muş, Niğde, Sakarya, Samsun, Sinop, Tekirdağ (Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı, 2015; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Austria, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, European Türkiye, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan, Lithuania, Macedonia, Montenegro, Moldavia, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine, Yugoslavia. **Asia:** Azerbaijan, Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Georgia, Iran,. **North Africa:** Morocco (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013).

Genus: *Aphanosoma* A. Costa, 1842

***Aphanosoma italicum* A. Costa, 1842**

Material examined: Amasya: Sarıyar, 19.05.2021, 1♂. **Taşova:** Çalkaya, 27.05.2021, 3♂♂, 4♀♀.

Number of localites: 2

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Bartın, Çankırı, Edirne, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Karabük, Kastamonu Kırklareli, Konya, Kütahya, Sinop, Tekirdağ (Lodos et al., 2003; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı, 2015).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, European Türkiye, Greece, Italy, Macedonia, Moldavia, Romania, Russia, Switzerland, Türkiye. **Asia:** Armenia, Asian Türkiye, Georgia (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013).

Genus: *Brachycoleus* Fieber, 1858***Brachycoleus decolor* Reuter, 1887****Material examined:** Taşova: Yeşilyurt, 27.05.2021, 1♀.**Number of localities:** 1**Distribution in Türkiye:** Adana, Ağrı, Ankara Amasya, Bayburt, Bursa, Bilecik, Bitlis, Çankırı, Diyarbakır, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Hatay, Iğdır, Kahramanmaraş, Kastamonu Kars, Kayseri, Kırkkale, Konya Nevşehir, Uşak, Yozgat (Önder, 1976; Altınayar, 1981; Lodos et al., 2003; Kıyak et al., 2004; Önder et al., 2006; Kıyak & Akar 2010; Matocq et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Yazıcı, 2015; Yazıcı & Yıldırım, 2016).**Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe:** Albania, Austria, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech, European Kazakhstan, European Türkiye, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Macedonia, Moldavia, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Azerbaijan, China, Georgia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye Kirgizia Russia, Tadzhikistan, Uzbekistan (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013; Luis, 2013).**Genus: *Capsus* Fabricius, 1803*****Capsus ater* (Linnaeus, 1758)****Material examined:** Amasya: Ezinepazar, 19.05.2021, 1♂.**Number of localities:** 1**Distribution in Türkiye:** Bartın, Bursa, Edirne, Erzurum, Kırklareli, Mersin, Tekirdağ (Lodos et al., 2003; Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı & Yıldırım, 2016).**Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe:** Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European Türkiye, Finland, France, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldavia, Montenegro, The Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Asian Türkiye, Georgia, Russia. Extralimital: North America (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013).**Genus: *Closterotomus* Fieber, 1858*****Closterotomus fulvomaculatus* (De Geer, 1773)****Material examined:** Amasya: Amasya Castle, 10.05.2022, 7♂♂.**Number of localities:** 1**Distribution in Türkiye:** Ankara, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bilecik, Bolu, Bursa, Çankırı, Düzce, Edirne, İstanbul, Kastamonu, Kırklareli, Kocaeli, Kütahya, Sakarya, Uşak, Zonguldak (Önder et al., 2006; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Yücel & Kivan, 2018).**Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe:** Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European Türkiye, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Lawia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldavia, Montenegro, The Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia,

Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Korea. **Extralimital:** North America (Alaska, N Canada) (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013).

***Closterotomus krueperi* (Reuter, 1880)**

Material examined: Amasya: Boğazköy, 18.05.2021, 1♀.

Number of localities: 1

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Aydın, Balıkesir, Burdur, Diyarbakır, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kütahya, Mersin, Muğla, Osmaniye, Uşak (Önder et al., 2006).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: European Türkiye, Greece. **Asia:** Asian Türkiye, Cyprus, Lebanon?, (Kerzhner et al., 1999).

***Closterotomus norwegicus* (Gmelin, 1790)**

Material examined: Amasya: Tatar, 19.05.2022, 1♂; Keşlik, 22.06.2022, 1♂; Sarıyar, 22.06.2022, 1♀; Ezinepazar, 22.06.2022, 1♀.

Number of localities: 4

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bilecik, Bolu, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Denizli, Edirne, Elâzığ, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hatay, İçel, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Kastamonu, Kırklareli, Kilis, Kocaeli, Kütahya, Muğla, Osmaniye, Samsun, Sinop, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Zonguldak (Önder, 1976; Önder et al., 2006; Lodos et al., 2003; Yazıcı, 2015; Çerçi et al., 2018).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Abania, Andorra!, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European Türkiye, Faeroe Isles, Finland, France, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lawia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Macedonia, Moldavia, Montenegro, The Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Asian Türkiye, Cyprus, Israel, Jordan, Syria. North Africa: Algeria, Azores, Cyprus, Egypt, Libya, Morocco, Madeira, Tunisia. **Extralimital:** North America, Australia, New Zealand, Tristan da Cunha (Wagner, 1970-71; Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2006; Önder et al., 2006; Aukema et al., 2013; Heckmann et al., 2015).

***Closterotomus reuteri* (Horvâth, 1882)**

Material examined: Amasya: Amasya Castle, 28.04.2020, 1♀; 10.05.2022, 1♀.

Number of localities: 1

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Bilecik, Bolu, Bursa, Karabük, Kütahya, Sakarya, Sinop, Zonguldak (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Bulgaria, Macedonia, Serbia. **Asia:** Asian Türkiye (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013).

Genus: *Horistus* Fieber, 1860**Subgenus: *Primihoristus* Chérot, 1997*****Horistus (Primihoristus) orientalis* (Gmelin 1790)**

Material examined: Amasya: Boğazköy, 18.05.2021, 6♀♀; Amasya Castle, 28.04.2022, 1♀; 10.05.2022, 4♀♀, 14.05.2022, 1♀.

Number of localites: 3

Distribution in Türkiye: Ankara, Antalya, Bursa, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elâzığ, Erzurum, Kahramanmaraş, Kayseri, Kırşehir, Kırıkkale, Mardin, Mersin, Nevşehir, Niğde (Özgen, 2012; Matocq et al. 2014; Yazıcı, 2015; Çerçi et al. 2018).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, European Türkiye, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Malta, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Ukraine. **Asia:** Asian Türkiye, Israel. **North Africa:** Algeria, Egypt, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia (Wagner, 1970-71; Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013).

Genus: *Liocoris* Fieber, 1858***Liocoris tripustulatus* (Fabricius, 1781)**

Material examined: Amasya: Boğazköy, 28.06.2021, 1♂, 3♀♀; Sarıyar, 22.06.2022, 9♂♂, 7♀♀; **Taşova:** Borabay Gölü, 29.08.2021, 1♀.

Number of localites: 3

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bilecik, Bitlis, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hakkâri, Hatay, İçel, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Konya, Kayseri, Kütahya, Manisa, Mardin, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Trabzon, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Önder, 1970; 1976; Önder et al., 1981; Kıyak, 1990; Lodos et al., 2003; Yazıcı, 2015; Kıyak & Akar, 2010; Tezcan et al., 2010; Matocq et al., 2014; Maral & Gökçe 2021).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European Türkiye, Finland, France, GreatGreat Britain, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Macedonia, Montenegro, Moldavia, The Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, Syria, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013).

Genus: *Lygus* Hahn, 1833***Lygus gemellatus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Material examined: Amasya: Dadı, 21.04.2021, 2♂♂; Uygur, 19.05.2021, 5♀♀, 8♂♂; Sarıyar, 19.05.2021, 3♀♀, 2♂♂; 22.06.2022, 3♂♂, 2♀♀; Mahmatlar, 05.07.2021, 1♂, 5♀♀; Karasenir, 09.09.2021, 6♀♀, 5♂♂; Ormanbağları, 09.09.2021, 1♀; 18.06.2022, 2♂♂, 1♀; Koza Mahallesi, 09.09.2021, 6♂♂, 3♀♀; 17.09.2022, 1♂; Kapıkaya,

09.09.2021, 2♀♀, 1♂; Tatar, 19.05.2021, 7♀♀; 22.06.2022, 4♀♀, 1♂; Ezinepazar, 22.06.2022, 10♂♂, 4♀♀; Gözlek, 03.09.2021, 13♀♀, 4♂♂; İpekköy, 12.09.2021, 1♂, 1♀; 22.05.2022 2♂♂; 18.06.2022, 7♂♂, 12♀♀; Keşlik, 22.06.2022, 1♂; İlyasköy, 05.07.2021, 16♂♂, 6♀♀; Helvacı Mahallesi, 29.07.2022, 3♂♂, 3♀♀; Şahinkayası, 03.10.2022, 1♀; Ziyaret Kasabası, 25.10.2022, 1♀; Bağlıca, 26.07.2022, 7♀♀, 9♂♂. **Merzifon:** Alışar, 20.08.2021, 1♂; Aktarla, 20.08.2021, 7♀♀, 34♂♂. **Taşova:** Kızgüldüren, 10.07.2021, 1♀, 1♂; Destek Stream, 28.06.2022, 3♂♂; Hacıbey Village, 10.07.2021, 1♀, 2♂♂; Sepetli, 27.05.2021, 1♀. **Suluova:** Saygılı, 28.06.2021, 1♂; Deveci, 20.08.2021, 10♂♂, 3♀♀; Erarslan, 28.06.2021, 1♂; Yüzbeyi, 28.06.2021, 1♀. **Göynücek:** Merkez, 03.09.2021, 8♂♂; Şarklı, 03.09.2021, 1♂; İkizyaka, 03.09.2021 15♂♂ 6♀♀; Yeniköy, 03.09.2021, 2♀♀, 18♂♂.

Number of localities: 44

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Bayburt, Bitlis, Bolu, Çanakkale, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Edirne, Elâzığ, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Iğdır, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Kayseri, Kütahya, Konya, Muğla, Muş, Nevşehir, Siirt, Tekirdağ, Uşak, Yozgat (Bingöl, 1978; Altınayar, 1981; Önder et al., 2006; Maral, 2007; Matocq & Özgen, 2010; Fent, 2011; Yazıcı, 2015; Yazıcı & Yıldırım, 2016; Özgen et al., 2020; Kaçar & Dursun, 2022; Kıyak, 2022).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European Kazakhstan, European Türkiye, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldavia, The Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Afghanistan, Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, China, Cyprus, Georgia, Iran, Kirgizia, Mongolia, Russia, Syria, Tadzhiistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan. **North Africa:** Algeria, Madeira, Morocco, Tunisia. **Extralimital:** North India, Nepal, Pakistan (Wagner, 1970-71; Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013; Luis, 2013; Heckmann et al., 2015).

***Lygus pratensis* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Amasya: Dadı, 21.04.2021, 2♀♀; Şahinkayası (Kızılca), 21.04.2021, 1♂; İpekköy, 16.05.2021, 1♀; 12.09.2021, 1♂; 18.06.2022, 3♂♂, 1♀; Keşlik, 19.05.2021, 1♂; Sarıyar, 19.05.2021, 1♀; 22.06.2022, 1♀; Mahmatlar, 05.07.2021, 1♂, 2♀♀; İlyasköy, 05.07.2021, 5♂♂; Sevincer, 05.07.2021, 6♂♂, 2♀♀; Boğazköy, 15.08.2021, 1♂; Gözlek, 03.09.2021, 1♀; Karasenir, 09.09.2021, 1♀; Kapıkaya, 09.09.2021, 10♂, 3♀♀; Ormanbağları, 09.09.2021, 2♂♂, 2♀♀; Amasya Castle, 10.05.2022, 1♀; Ezinepazar, 22.06.2022, 4♂♂. **Taşova:** Hacıbey Village, 10.07.2021, 1♀, 2♂♂; Kızgüldüren, 10.07.2021, 1♀, 1♂; Boraboy Gölü, 29.08.2021, 3♀♀. **Göynücek:** Merkez, 03.09.2021, 5♂♂; Yeniköy, 03.09.2021, 2♀♀. **Merzifon:** Alışar, 20.08.2021, 2♂♂; Yalnız Village, 20.08.2021, 1♂; Aktarla, 20.08.2021, 22♂♂, 2♀♀; Çobanören Yolu, 14.09.2021, 1♂. **Suluova:** Erarslan, 28.06.2021, 1♂.

Number of localities: 31

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Adıyaman, Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bilecik, Bingöl, Bitlis, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hakkâri, Hatay, İçel, İstanbul, İzmir, Isparta, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kırklareli, Kırşehir, Kilis, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Muğla, Muş, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Samsun, Siirt, Sinop, Şanlıurfa, Trabzon, Tunceli,

Uşak, Van, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Önder, 1976; Bingöl, 1978; Giray, 1980; Altınayar, 1981; Önder et al., 1981, 1984; Kıyak, 1990; Güçlü et al., 1995; Tamer et al., 1998; Kaçar, 2019; Beyaz, 2000; Lodos et al., 2003; Atlıhan & Özgökçe, 2003; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı, 2015; Koca & Kütük, 2020; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Kaçar & Dursun, 2022).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European Kazakhstan, European Türkiye, Finland, France, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland?, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Malta, Moldavia, The Netherlands, Montenegro, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Afghanistan, Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, China, Cyprus, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Kirgizia, Mongolia, Russia, Syria, Tadzhikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan. **North Africa:** Algeria, Canary Isles, Morocco. **Extralimital:** India (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013; Heckmann et al., 2015).

***Lygus rugulipennis* Poppius, 1911**

Material examined: Amasya: Dadı, 21.04.2021, 2♀; Uygur, 19.05.2021, 4♂♂, 5♀♀; Mahmatlar, 05.07.2021, 1♀; Sevincer, 05.07.2021, 1♀, 2♂♂; İlyasköy, 05.07.2021, 5♀♀; Karasenir, 09.09.2021, 2♂♂, 1♀; Kapıkaya, 09.09.2021, 2♀♀; Koza Mahallesi, 09.09.2021, 1♀; İpekköy, 16.05.2021, 1♀; 12.09.2021, 1♂, 1♀; Merkez, 12.10.2021, 1♀; Sanayi Sitesi, 24.08.2021, 1♂; Tatar, 19.05.2021, 1♀; 22.06.2022, 1♀; Gözlek, 03.09.2021, 1♂, 4♀♀. **Suluova:** Yedikır Baraj, 07.09.2022, 1♂; Yüzbeyi, 28.06.2021, 17♂♂, 7♀♀; Erarslan, 28.06.2021, 1♂; Deveci, 20.08.2021, 4♀♀, 3♂♂. **Merzifon:** Aktarla, 20.08.2021, 8♀♀, 2♂♂; Alishar, 20.08.2021, 1♀; Kara Mustafa Paşa Village, 14.09.2021, 2♀♀. **Taşova:** Kızgüldüren Village, 10.07.2021, 9♂♂, 7♀♀; Yeşilyurt, 27.05.2021, 1♀. **Göynücek:** İkiyaka, 03.09.2021, 2♀♀, 4♂♂; Yeniköy, 03.09.2021, 1♀.

Number of localities: 26

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Adıyaman, Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Aksaray, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Bartın, Bilecik, Bingöl, Bitlis, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çankırı, Çanak-kale, Çorum, Denizli, Düzce, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Giresun, Hakkâri, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kırklareli, Kırşehir, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Malatya, Muş, Nevşehir, Niğde, Sakarya, Samsun, Sinop, Şanlıurfa, Tekirdağ, Tunceli, Uşak, Van, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Önder, 1976; Bingöl, 1978; ; Giray, 1980; Önder et al., 1981; 1984; Özbek & Alaoğlu, 1987; Kıyak, 1990; Tamer et al., 1998; Yıldırım et al., 1999; Atlıhan & Özgökçe 2003; Lodos et al., 2003; Tezcan et al., 2010; Atlıhan et al., 2011; Sert et al., 2013; Yazıcı, 2015; Çerçi et al., 2018; Kaçar, 2019).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European Kazakhstan, European Türkiye, Faeroe Isles, Finland, France, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Montenegro, Moldavia, , The Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, China, Georgia, Iran, Korea, Mongolia, Russia. **Extralimital:** North America (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013; Luis, 2013; Heckmann et al., 2015).

Genus: *Orthops* Fieber, 1858**Subgenus: *Orthops* Fieber, 1858*****Orthops (s.str.) basalis* (A. Costa, 1853)**

Material examined: Amasya: Amasya Castle, 28.04.2022, 2♀♀; Sarıyar, 22.06.2022, 1♀.

Number of localities: 2

Distribution in Türkiye: Ankara, Artvin, Burdur, Erzurum, Samsun (Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı, 2015; Patlar et al., 2022).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium!, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European Türkiye, Finland, France, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Montenegro, Moldavia, The Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Asian Kazakhstan, Georgia, Iran, Russia, Saudi Arabia, Türkiye, Yemen. **North Africa:** Algeria, Canary Isles, Madeira. **Extralimital:** North America (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013).

***Orthops (s.str.) campestris* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Amasya: Sarıyar, 22.06.2022, 1♀. **Suluova:** Saygılı, 28.06.2021, 1♂, 2♀♀; Erarslan, 28.06.2022, 1♀, 1♀; Yüzbey, 28.06.2022, 2♀♀.

Number of localities: 4

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bilecik, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çorum, Denizli, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Giresun, Hatay, İçel, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Manisa, Nevşehir, Niğde, Sakarya, Samsun, Tokat, Uşak, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Önder, 1970; 1976; Giray, 1980; Önder et al., 1981; Özbek & Alaoğlu 1987; Güçlü et al., 1995; Lodos et al., 2003; Tezcan et al., 2010; Yazıcı, 2015).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European Türkiye, Finland, France, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldavia, The Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran, Russia. **North Africa:** Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013).

***Orthops (s.str.) kalmii* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Amasya: Sarıyar, 22.06.2022, 1♂; Kaşka Village, 26.07.2022, 1♀, 1♂. **Suluova:** Erarslan, 28.06.2021, 2♀♀; Saygılı, 28.06.2021, 2♀♀.

Number of localities: 4

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Artvin, Bilecik, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Erzurum, Eskişehir, İçel, İstanbul, İzmir, Hatay, Gaziantep, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Kastamonu,

Kayseri, Kocaeli, Mardin, Nevşehir, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Sinop, Tekirdağ, Trabzon, Uşak Yozgat, Zonguldak (Önder, 1970; 1976; Giray, 1980; Önder et al., 1981; Yıldırım et al., 1999; Lodos et al., 2003; Tezcan et al., 2010; Yazıcı, 2015).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European Türkiye, Finland, France, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldavia, The Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Armenia, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Cyprus, Georgia, Iran, Russia, Turkmenistan. **North Africa:** Algeria, Madeira, Morocco, Tunisia (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013).

Subgenus: *Montanorthops* Ghauri, 1978

***Orthops* (*Montanorthops*) *forelii* Fieber, 1858**

Material examined: Amasya: Boğazköy, 28.06.2021, 1♀, 1♂; Keşlik, 22.06.2022, 1♀; Sarıyar, 22.06.2022, 1♀.

Number of localities: 3

Distribution in Türkiye: Erzurum, Kayseri (Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı, 2015).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Austria, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Macedonia, Moldavia, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Armenia, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Georgia. (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013; Derjanschi, 2016).

Genus: *Phytocoris* Fallén, 1814

Subgenus: *Ktenocoris* Wagner, 1954

***Phytocoris* (*Ktenocoris*) *varipes* Boheman, 1852**

Material examined: Amasya: İlyasköy, 05.07.2021, 1♀.

Number of localities: 1

Distribution in Türkiye: Artvin, Kırklareli (Önder et al., 1976).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia?, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, European Kazakhstan, European Türkiye, France, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldavia, Montenegro, The Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Armenia, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Turkmenistan. Extralimital: North America (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013).

Genus: *Polymerus* Hahn, 1831

Subgenus: *Polymerus* Hahn, 1831

***Polymerus* (*s.str.*) *holosericeus* Hahn, 1831**

Material examined: Amasya: Helvacı Mahallesi, 29.07.2022, 1♂.

Number of localities: 1

Distribution in Türkiye: Edirne, Kırklareli (Önder et al., 1984; 2006).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, European Türkiye, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia?, Lithuania, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, Moldavia, The Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Azerbaijan, Georgia (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013).

Subgenus: Poeciloscytus Fieber, 1858

Polymerus (Poeciloscytus) brevicornis (Reuter, 1879)

Material examined: Taşova: Çaydibi, 27.05.2021, 1♀.

Number of localities: 1

Distribution in Türkiye: Bartın, Konya (Önder et al., 2006).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Austria, Bulgaria, Denmark, European Türkiye, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy?, Latvia, Macedonia, Moldavia, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Afghanistan, Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, China, Georgia, Iran, Kirgizia, Korea, Russia, Tadzhikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013).

Polymerus (Poeciloscytus) cognatus (Fieber, 1858)

Material examined: Amasya: Gözlek, 03.09.2021, 2♂♂.

Number of localities: 1

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Ağrı, Ankara, Antalya, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Burdur, Bursa, Çankırı, Çorum, Düzce, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, İstanbul, Iğdır, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırklareli, Kocaeli, Konya, Manisa, Mersin, Nevşehir, Niğde, Sakarya, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Önder et al., 1981; 2006; Yazıcı, 2015).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Austria, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, European Kazakhstan, European Türkiye, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia?, Lithuania, Macedonia, Malta, Moldavia, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, China, Georgia, Iran, Israel, Japan, Kirgizia, Korea, Mongolia, Poland, Russia, Tadzhikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan. **North Africa:** Algeria, Azores, Morocco, Tunisia. **Extralimital:** North America (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013; Carapezza & Mifsud, 2015; Heckmann et al., 2015).

Genus: Notostira Fieber, 1858

Notostira erratica (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined: Suluova: Ayrancı, 28.06.2021, 1♀.

Number of localities: 1

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Ağrı, Ankara, Artvin, Bartın, Bilecik, Bursa, Çankırı, Erzurum, İzmir, Karabük, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Konya, Siirt, Yozgat (Lodos et al., 2003; Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı, 2015).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Andorra, Austria, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European Kazakhstan?, Finland, France, Great Britain?, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Macedonia, Montenegro, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Armenia, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran, Russia, Turkmenistan (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013).

Genus: *Stenodema* Laporte, 1833

Subgenus: *Stenodema* Laporte, 1833

***Stenodema* (s.str.) *sericans* (Fieber, 1861)**

Material examined: Taşova: Borabay Gölü, 29.08.2021, 1♀ 1♂; Sepetli, 27.05.2021, 1♀.

Number of localities: 2

Distribution in Türkiye: Bursa, Düzce, İstanbul, Kocaeli, Sakarya (Önder et al., 1981).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Andorra, Austria, Bosnia Hercegovina, Croatia, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Liechtenstein, Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Asian Türkiye (Önder et al., 1981; Kerzhner et al., 1999; Aukema et al., 2013).

Subgenus: *Brachystira* Fieber, 1858

***Stenodema* (*Brachystira*) *calcarata* (Fallén, 1807)**

Material examined: Amasya: Ezinepazar, 22.06.2022, 1♂; Tatar, 22.06.2022, 2♂♂, 1♀. **Merzifon:** Çavundur, 06.09.2022, 1♀. **Taşova:** Arpa Stream, 27.05.2021, 1♀; Kızgüldüren, 10.07.2021, 3♀♀ 2 ♂♂; Borabay Gölü, 29.08.2021, 2♀♀ 1♂; Destek Stream, 28.06.2022, 1♂.

Number of localities: 7

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bitlis, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Diyarbakır, Elâzığ, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, İçel, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kilis, Kırklareli, Konya, Kütahya, Muğla, Niğde, Rize, Sakarya, Samsun, Sinop, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Uşak, Yozgat, (Önder et al., 1981; Yardım, 1990; Lodos et al., 2003; Önder, 2006; Tezcan et al., 2010; Fent, 2011; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı, 2015).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European Kazakhstan, European Türkiye, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Macedonia, Moldavia, Montenegro, Norway, The Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. **Asia:** Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, China, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Israel,

Japan, Kirgizia, Korea, Lebanon, Russia, Syria, Tadzhikistan, Uzbekistan. **North Africa:** Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia (Wagner, 1970-71; Kerzhner et al., 1999; Goula & Serra, 2010; Aukema et al., 2013; Luis, 2013).

Genus: *Trigonotylus* Fieber, 1858

***Trigonotylus pulchellus* (Hahn, 1834)**

Material examined: Amasya: İlyasköy, 05.07.2021, 2♀♀; Mahmatlar, 05.07.2021, 2♀♀; Kaşka Village, 26.07.2022, 1♀. **Taşova:** Çaydibi, 27.05.2021, 2♀♀; Arpa Stream, 27.05.2021, 1♀; Kızgüldüren, 10.07.2021, 2♀♀, 1♂.

Number of localities: 1

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Ağrı, Aksaray, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Bartın, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Kayseri, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Siirt, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Önder et al., 2006; Matocq & Özgen 2010, Matocq et al., 2014, Yazıcı, 2015; Çerçi et al., 2018).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, European Türkiye, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Macedonia, Moldavia, Montenegro, The Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Ukraine. **North Africa:** Algeria, Egypt, Morocco, Tunisia. **Asia:** Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, China, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Kirgizia, Tadzhikistan, Uzbekistan (Wagner, 1970-71; Kerzhner et al., 1999; Goula & Serra, 2010; Aukema et al., 2013; Luis, 2013).

Genus: *Camponotidea* Reuter, 1879

***Camponotidea saundersi* (Puton, 1874)**

Material examined: Amasya: Kaleköy, 28.04.2021, 2♀♀, 67♂♂; Sariyar, 19.05.2021, 2♂♂. **Taşova:** Çalkaya, 27.05.2021, 21♀♀; Çaydibi, 27.05.2021, 6♀♀; Yeşilyurt, 27.05.2021, 8♂♂, 1♀.

Number of localities: 5

Distribution in Türkiye: Ankara, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Erzincan, Gaziantep, Hatay, İzmir, Muğla, Osmaniye, Siirt, Tekirdağ (Önder et al., 2006).

Distribution in Palearctic Region: Europe: Albania, Croatia, European Türkiye, Greece, Italy, Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, Slovenia. **Asia:** Asian Türkiye, Iran, Israel, Syria (Kerzhner et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006; Aukema et al., 2013; Mohammadi et al., 2018; Dioli & Samaritakis, 2021).

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In this study, the research material consists of samples collected from 54 different localities around Amasya province between 2020 and 2022. As a result of the determination of the material collected in Amasya province, 29 species belonging to 15 genera of Mirinae sub-family were recorded. Of those, 22 species are new records for the research area of Amasya.

The rare species *Polymerus holosericeus* was known only from Edirne and Kırklareli from the Thrace Region of Türkiye (Önder et al., 1984; 2006). It is widely distributed in Europe and only from Azerbaijan and Georgia in Asia. In this study, it was recorded for the first time from Anatolia of Türkiye. The species *Adelphocoris detritus*, *Adelphocoris quadripunctatus*, *Capsus ater*, *Closterotomus krueperi* and *Orthops forelli* are new records for the Miridae faunae of the Black Sea Region. The species *Closterotomus fulvomaculatus*, *Phytocoris varipes*, *Polymerus brevicornis*, *Notostira erratica* and *Stenodema sericans* are also new records for the Miridae faunae of Central Black Sea Region.

Among the species *Polymerus holosericeus*, *Polymerus brevicornis*, *Adelphocoris detritus*, *Phytocoris varipes* and *Orthops forelli* are rarely distributed and *Adelphocoris lineolatus*, *Lygus gemellatus*, *L. pratensis*, *L. rugulipennis* are widely distributed and frequently found in Türkiye and also in our present study are. The relationship of the samples with the plants is given in table 1.

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